

SHOULD THE TIME OF VIGOROUS PHYSICAL ACTIVITY BE MULTIPLIED BY TWO IN CLASSIFYING OF PRACTICE BY IPAQ-SHORT VERSION?

¿DEBERÍA MULTIPLICARSE POR DOS EL TIEMPO DE ACTIVIDAD FÍSICA INTENSA EN LA CLASIFICACIÓN DE PRÁCTICA IPAQ-VERSIÓN CORTA?

O TEMPO DE ATIVIDADE FÍSICA VIGOROSA DEVE SER MULTIPLICADO POR DOIS NA CLASSIFICAÇÃO DE PRÁTICA PELO IPAQ-VERSÃO CURTA?

Mariana da Silva Ferreira ¹
Thiago Ferreira de Sousa ²
Alex Carneiro Brandão ³
Gerleison Ribeiro Barros ⁴
Gildeene Silva Farias ⁵
Aline de Jesus Santos ⁶
Silvio Aparecido Fonseca ⁷

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Abstract

Practicing physical activity (PA) is essential for health, but many adults do not meet the minimum recommendations. The objective was to analyze the agreement between the criteria for classifying PA measured by the International Physical Activity Questionnaire (IPAQ), short version, with and without multiplying the time spent practicing at vigorous intensity by two, in comparison to the classification of in accordance with the guide for that instrument. A cross-sectional study was carried out with Brazilian university students. Comparisons between prevalences were performed using the McNemar test and levels of agreement using the Kappa (K) test. Participated 1,110 university students with an average age of 21.45 years. In general, the prevalence of insufficient PA practice (<150 min/week) was different in comparison with the IPAQ guideline (30.8% with

¹ Master in Physical Education from the Federal University of Triângulo Mineiro. Teacher at the Municipal Education Network of Teresina and Physical Education Professional at the Psychosocial Care Center.

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2054-2179> Contact: marianaferreira_83@hotmail.com

² Doctorate in Physical Education from the Federal University of Santa Catarina. Professor in the Postgraduate Program in Physical Education at the State University of Santa Cruz..

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9846-9661> Contact: tfsousa_thiago@yahoo.com.br

³ Doctoral student in Public Health at the Federal University of Santa Catarina. Master in Human Movement Sciences from the State University of Santa Catarina.

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-1358-719X> Contact: allexbrandao.c@gmail.com

⁴ Master in Physical Education from the Federal University of Triângulo Mineiro.

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5122-8625> Contact: efgerleison@hotmail.com

⁵ Doctoral student in Physical Education at São Judas Tadeu University. Master in Physical Education from the Federal University of Triângulo Mineiro. Professor at the Federal University of Piauí and at Estácio de Sá College.

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2810-2925> Contact: gilfarias28@hotmail.com

⁶ Master's student in Physical Education at the State University of Santa Cruz. Graduated in Physical Education from the Federal University of Recôncavo da Bahia.

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8195-2008> Contact: alinnetrindadeo@gmail.com

⁷ Doctorate in Physical Education from the Federal University of Santa Catarina. Professor in the Postgraduate Program in Physical Education at the State University of Santa Cruz.

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9903-6905> Contact: safonseca@uesc.br

multiplication by two; 31.6% without multiplication; and 36.7% per guide). These differences also occurred separately for each sex. There was approximately 92% agreement between classifications with and without multiplication with the guide criteria. Among men, PA with multiplication by two showed lower agreement ($K: 0.787$; $p: <0.001$; 91.59%) and among women, PA without multiplication by two showed greater agreement between classifications. It is concluded that there is substantial agreement between the classifications with and without multiplying the time spent practicing vigorous-intensity PA by two, especially among women, however, the prevalences differ from the classification criteria presented by the instrument guide.

Keywords: Motor Activity; Data Accuracy; Questionnaires.

Resumen

Practicar actividad física (AF) es fundamental para la salud, pero muchos adultos no cumplen las recomendaciones mínimas. El objetivo fue analizar la concordancia entre los criterios de clasificación de la AF medidos por el Cuestionario Internacional de Actividad Física (IPAQ), versión corta, con y sin multiplicar por dos el tiempo dedicado a practicar a intensidad vigorosa, en comparación con la clasificación de conformidad con la guía para ese instrumento. Se realizó un estudio transversal con estudiantes universitarios brasileños. Las comparaciones entre prevalencias se realizaron mediante la prueba de McNemar y los niveles de concordancia mediante la prueba Kappa (K). En este estudio participaron 1.110 estudiantes universitarios con una edad promedio de 21,45 años. En general, la prevalencia de práctica insuficiente de AF (<150 min/semana) fue diferente en comparación con la guía IPAQ (30,8% con multiplicación por dos; 31,6% sin multiplicación; y 36,7% por guía). Estas diferencias también se produjeron por separado para cada sexo. Hubo aproximadamente un 92% de acuerdo entre las clasificaciones con y sin multiplicación con los criterios de la guía. Entre los hombres, la AF con multiplicación por dos mostró menor concordancia ($K: 0,787$; $p: <0,001$; 91,59%) y entre las mujeres, la AF sin multiplicación por dos mostró mayor concordancia entre clasificaciones. Se concluye que existe acuerdo sustancial entre las clasificaciones con y sin multiplicar por dos el tiempo dedicado a practicar AF de intensidad vigorosa, especialmente entre las mujeres, sin embargo, las prevalencias difieren de los criterios de clasificación presentados por la guía del instrumento.

Palabras clave: Actividad Motora; Exactitud de los Datos; Cuestionarios.

Resumo

A prática de atividade física (AF) é essencial para a saúde, mas muitos adultos não cumprem as recomendações mínimas. O objetivo deste estudo foi analisar a concordância entre os critérios de classificação da AF mensurada pelo *International Physical Activity Questionnaire* (IPAQ), versão curta, com e sem a multiplicação do tempo de prática em intensidade vigorosa por dois, em comparação a classificação de acordo com o guia do referido instrumento. Realizou-se um estudo de delineamento transversal com estudantes universitários brasileiros. As comparações entre as prevalências foram realizadas via teste McNemar e os níveis de concordância por meio do teste Kappa (K). Participaram deste estudo 1.110 universitários com média de idade de 21,45 anos. De modo geral, as prevalências de prática de AF em nível insuficiente (<150 min/sem) foram diferentes nas comparações com a diretriz do IPAQ (30,8% com a multiplicação por dois; 31,6% sem a multiplicação; e 36,7% pelo guia). Essas diferenças também ocorreram em separado para cada sexo. Houve concordância de aproximadamente 92% entre as classificações com e sem multiplicação com o critério do guia. Entre os homens, a AF com a multiplicação por dois demonstrou menor concordância ($K: 0,787$; $p: <0,001$; 91,59%) e entre as mulheres, a AF sem a multiplicação por dois apresentou maior concordância entre as classificações. Conclui-se que há concordância substancial entre as classificações com e sem a multiplicação do tempo de prática de AF em intensidade vigorosa por dois, especialmente entre mulheres, porém, as prevalências divergem do critério de classificação apresentado pelo guia do instrumento.

Palavras-chave: Atividade Motora; Confiabilidade dos Dados; Questionário.

Introduction

Physical activity is a crucial health-related behavior (Posadzki et al., 2020; Warburton & Bredin, 2017) that, when practiced regularly, can positively impact protection against chronic diseases such as systemic arterial hypertension and diabetes (Saco-Ledo et al., 2022; Gallardo-Gómez et al., 2024), while also strengthening the immune system against opportunistic infections (Cerasola, Argano & Corrao, 2022). According to the World Health Organization (WHO, 2022), 27.5% of adults worldwide do not engage in sufficient physical activity to achieve health benefits. Studies indicate that college students are prone to insufficient physical activity, and this behavior tends to persist over time without targeted interventions (Keating et al., 2005; Pengpid et al., 2015; Ferreira et al., 2020).

Thus, this population tends not to meet the physical activity recommendations established by both the World Health Organization (2020) and the Brazilian Ministry of Health (2021). These organizations recommend that adults aged ≥ 18 years should accumulate at least 150-300 minutes of moderate-intensity aerobic physical activity; or at least 75-150 minutes of vigorous-intensity aerobic physical activity; or an equivalent combination of moderate and vigorous-intensity physical activity throughout the week (Lima; Levy; Luiz, 2014).

To measure low levels of physical activity among university students, epidemiological studies (Sousa, 2011) have employed the (*International Physical Activity Questionnaire – IPAQ*), which enables assessment of physical activity in terms of both time spent (hours/minutes per week) and metabolic equivalents (METs) measured in minutes per week (MET-min/week) (International Physical Activity Questionnaire – IPAQ, 2005).

To classify physical activity time using the short version of IPAQ, vigorous-intensity activities are typically weighted by a factor of two. This estimates whether or not the recommended minimum of 150 minutes per week at moderate to vigorous intensity is met (Oliveira et al., 2022; Alhammad et al., 2023; Samarkandi, 2022). This methodological procedure was initially presented by Armstrong, Bauman and Davies (2000), and followed by Craig et al. (2003) and Hallal et al. (2003). On the other hand, despite the practicality of this classification method, alternative criteria can be employed, such as MET considerations

and the categorization into three intensity levels (low, moderate, and high), which account for variables including frequency, duration, and intensity, as outlined in the IPAQ guidelines (IPAQ, 2005).

In a previous study, Alves et al. (2010) demonstrated that engaging in 150 minutes or more per week of vigorous-intensity physical activity (weighted by two), as assessed through the short-form IPAQ, showed agreement with IPAQ's five-category classification system (sedentary, irregularly active B, irregularly active A, active, and very active) (Matsudo et al., 2001), with a kappa coefficient of 0.85 (IC95%: 0,83 – 0,87). However, there was disagreement between participants classified as sufficiently active according to the score and those classified as insufficiently active based on Matsudo et al.'s criteria. (2001) in 7.5% of the sample.

Therefore, since the classification method of a measure is crucial for identifying physically inactive risk groups, it is essential to understand potential differences in the weighting strategy of vigorous intensity, whether doubled or not, in physical activity classification through scoring, compared to the criteria established by the IPAQ guidelines (IPAQ, 2005). Therefore, this study aimed to analyze the agreement in physical activity classification between the short version of IPAQ, with and without doubling vigorous-intensity practice time, compared to the original IPAQ guidelines (IPAQ, 2005), among university students from a Brazilian public institution.

Methods

This cross-sectional study stems from the research "Lifestyle Profile and Quality of Life of Students at the Federal University of Triângulo Mineiro (UFTM)" conducted in 2018. The study was approved by the UFTM research ethics committee (Opinion number: 2.402.734).

The target population consisted of undergraduate students enrolled in the first semester of 2018 at the Uberaba campus, Minas Gerais (N: 5.952). The minimum sample size was estimated considering a prevalence of 50% to obtain the largest possible sample size, with a 95% confidence level and an acceptable sampling error of three percentage points. The sample was then increased by 20% to minimize losses and by an additional 10%

for association studies. Therefore, the sample analyzed was 1,195 university students. Replacement procedures were implemented for those who declined participation.

The calculated sample size was distributed among the institution's 25 courses, considering the proportionality of the courses in the institution. All university students aged 18 years or older were included in the study, regardless of physical condition. After tabulating the data, university students were excluded if they reported having a distance learning or technical course with the university, those who reported having a higher education diploma and those who reported having a course that was not in the city where the institution was based, as we believe that this group of people with these characteristics do not experience or have experienced a daily routine at a university. This exclusion information was included in the informed consent form.

Data collection team training was carried out in March 2018. The team was made up of 11 members (undergraduate and postgraduate students in Physical Education) from UFTM. Information was obtained through the application of the instrument between the months of April, May, June and July 2018. The questionnaire was applied in the classroom, in groups of up to 30 university students or individually, assisted by an administrator. The average time to complete participation was 15 minutes.

Data were collected using a paper-and-pencil instrument comprising questions from the Health and Quality of Life Indicators for Academics (ISAQ-A) questionnaire, which underwent face and content validity testing, clarity assessment, pre-testing, and one-week test-retest reliability, showing satisfactory indicators for use among university students (Sousa et al., 2013). The IPAQ, which demonstrates satisfactory internal consistency for estimating physical activity in university students (Sousa; Farias; Santos, 2024) and has been validated for use in young adults (Matsudo et al., 2001), was also employed. Sociodemographic characteristics and university affiliation data were collected.

In this study, the main investigation variable was physical activity. The classification of physical activity considered the most current IPAQ guidelines (IPAQ, 2005), as shown in Table 1. Following classification, the variable was dichotomized into high/moderate and low categories to align with the time-based scoring system.

Table 1. Physical activity classification criteria according to the IPAQ Guide guidelines (2005).

Category	Classification Criteria
Low	College students who did not reach the moderate or high level of physical activity categories
Moderate	For classification, moderate level, it is necessary to meet at least one of the criteria below: a) 3 or more days of vigorous physical activity of at least 20 minutes per day. b) 5 or more days of moderate intensity physical activity and/or walking for at least 30 minutes per day. c) 5 or more days of some combination of walking, moderate or vigorous intensity, with a minimum of 600 MET-min/week.
High	For classification, high level, it is necessary to meet at least one of the criteria below: a) Vigorous physical activity for at least 3 days and a minimum of 1,500 MET-min/week. b) 7 or more days of physical activity (walking, moderate or vigorous), with a minimum of 3,000 MET-min/week.

Source: Author's work

The two test variables were obtained by scoring (summing) physical activity time, considering minutes spent walking and in moderate-to-vigorous intensity activities, calculated by multiplying days of practice by daily practice duration in minutes (hours were converted to minutes). Physical activity was categorized into two groups: up to 149 minutes per week and 150 minutes or more per week. Two analytical approaches were employed: one considering vigorous physical activity time doubled, as per previous studies (Armstrong et al., 2000; Craig et al., 2003; Hallal et al., 2003; Lima; Luiz, 2015), and another without this intensity multiplication.

The information for this study was entered into Excel software (version 2013). The study analyses were performed using SPSS software (version 25.0). Results were presented using descriptive statistics (absolute and relative frequencies, mean and standard deviation [SD]). The relative frequencies of physical activity categories were compared using McNemar's test according to IPAQ guidelines (IPAQ, 2005). The agreement level between tested variables and classification was assessed using Kappa (k) test. The following k test levels were considered: 0 to 0.20, mild; 0.21 to 0.40, fair; 0.41 to 0.60, moderate; 0.61 to 0.80, substantial; 0.81 to 1.00, almost perfect (Kottner et al., 2011). Analyses were conducted for the entire university student sample and separately by gender. The significance level adopted was 5%.

Results

A total of 1,110 undergraduate students participated in this study; however, physical activity data were missing for 16 participants. A total of 416 men participated (mean age 21.84 years; SD: 4.24 years; 18 to 54 years) and 673 women (mean age 21.18 years; SD: 3.98 years; 18 to 56 years). The total sample had a mean age of 21.45 years (SD: 4.10; 18 to 56 years). The prevalence of physical activities, with and without multiplying the vigorous intensity by two, and via the current classification of the instrument are presented in Table 1. Overall, insufficient physical activity levels were found in 30.8% of students when doubling the time, 31.6% without doubling, and 36.7% according to current guidelines. Physical activity prevalence rates differed when vigorous activity was doubled versus not doubled in IPAQ classification guidelines, both overall and when analyzed by sex.

Table 1. Comparison between the prevalence of physical activities according to different forms of classification. Uberaba, MG. 2018.

Variables	All		Men		Women	
	n (%)	*	n (%)	*	n (%)	*
Physical activity (multiplying vigorous intensity by two)		-		-		-
Up to 149 minutes/week	337 (30.8)		99 (23.8)		236 (35.1)	
150 or more minutes/week	757 (69.2)		317 (76.2)		437 (64.9)	
Physical activity (without doubling vigorous intensity)		-		-		-
Up to 149 minutes/week	346 (31.6)		105 (25.2)		239 (35.5)	
150 or more minutes/week	748 (68.4)		311 (74.8)		434 (64.5)	
Physical activity (current)		<0.001 ^a		<0.001 ^c		<0.001 ^a
		<0.001 ^b		0.001 ^d		<0.001 ^b
Low	402 (36.7)		124 (29.8)		275 (40.9)	
Moderate/High	692 (63.3)		292 (70.2)		398 (59.1)	

#: Prevalence; *p-value of the McNemar test; a: physical activity multiplied by two x physical activity current classification; b: physical activity without multiplying by two x physical activity current classification. **Source:** Author's work.

Table 2 presents the physical activity agreement levels for all university students in relation to the IPAQ guidelines, both with and without doubling the vigorous intensity scores. There was approximately 92% agreement (almost perfect) regardless of whether vigorous-intensity time was multiplied.

Table 2. Level of agreement between physical activity variables with and without multiplying vigorous intensity by 2 in relation to the IPAQ guide criterion in all university students. Uberaba, MG. 2018.

Variables tested	Classification variable Physical Activity (current)			K (p) %C
	Low n (%)	Moderate/ High n (%)		
Physical activity (multiplying vigorous intensity by two)				0.823 (<0.001) 92.05
Up to 149 minutes/week	326 (96.7)	11 (3.3)		
150 or more minutes/week	76 (10.0)	681 (90.0)		
Physical activity (without doubling vigorous intensity)				0.834 (<0.001) 92.50
Up to 149 minutes/week	333 (96.2)	13 (3.8)		
150 or more minutes/week	69 (9.2)	679 (90.8)		

#: Frequency; %C: Agreement; K: Kappa test; p: p-value of the Kappa test. **Source:** Author's work.

The levels of agreement between the tested physical activity criteria in relation to classification according to the instrument guidelines, separated by sex, are shown in Tables 3 (men) and 4 (women). Among men, physical activity with a multiplication of two for vigorous intensity demonstrated lower agreement when compared with the current classification guideline (k: 0.787; moderate agreement) (Table 3). Among women, physical activity without doubling the score for vigorous intensity showed higher classification agreement.

Table 3. Agreement level between physical activity variables with and without doubling vigorous intensity in relation to IPAQ guidelines criteria among male university students. Uberaba, MG. 2018.

Variables tested	Classification variable Physical Activity (current)			K (p) %C
	Low n (%)	Moderate/ High n (%)		
Physical activity (multiplying vigorous intensity by two)				0.787 (<0.001) 91.59
Up to 149 minutes/week	94 (94.9)	5 (5.1)		
150 or more minutes/week	30 (9.5)	287 (90.5)		
Physical activity (without doubling vigorous intensity)				0.814 (<0.001) 92.55
Up to 149 minutes/week	99 (94.3)	6 (5.7)		
150 or more minutes/week	25 (8.0)	286 (92.0)		

#: Frequency; %C: Agreement; K: Kappa test; p: p-value of the Kappa test. **Source:** Author's work,

Table 4. Agreement level between physical activity variables with and without doubling vigorous intensity in relation to IPAQ guidelines criteria among female university students. Uberaba, MG. 2018.

Variables tested	Classification variable Physical Activity (current)		
	Low n (%)	Moderate/ High n (%)	K (p) %C
Physical activity (multiplying vigorous intensity by two)			0.840 (<0.001) 92.42
Up to 149 minutes/week	230 (97.5)	6 (2.5)	
150 or more minutes/week	45 (10.3)	392 (89.7)	
Physical activity (without doubling vigorous intensity)			0.843 (<0.001) 92.57
Up to 149 minutes/week	232 (97.1)	7 (2.9)	
150 or more minutes/week	43 (9.9)	391 (90.1)	

#: Frequency; %C: Agreement; K: Kappa test; p: p-value of the Kappa test. **Source:** Author's work,

Discussion

This study demonstrated high levels of agreement between physical activity with and without doubling vigorous intensity when compared to physical activity classified according to the instrument's current guidelines. On the other hand, prevalence rates differed when comparing results with and without doubling vigorous-intensity activity according to IPAQ guidelines.

In this study, nearly perfect agreement levels were observed among all university students and women, both when applying a weighting factor of two for vigorous-intensity time and when this procedure was not used. In men, moderate agreement was observed when doubling vigorous-intensity activity time. It is interesting to note that these results converge with the study that estimated the level of agreement of the time score, with the multiplication by two of the vigorous intensity, in comparison with the old IPAQ criterion (sedentary, irregularly active B, irregularly active A, active and very active), with an agreement of 0.85 (IC95%: 0.83 – 0.87) (ALVES et al., 2010). Due to men's higher engagement in vigorous-intensity activities (Kretschmer et al., 2023; Bauman et al., 2009), doubling these scores led to greater discrepancies with the low physical activity category under current guidelines (IPAQ, 2005), suggesting caution in classifying this group as sufficiently active when they might actually belong in the low-level category.

The high percentage of agreement (>90%) between classifications, with and without doubling vigorous intensity scores, aligned with IPAQ guidelines, demonstrates the feasibility of using both time-scoring approaches. However, the prevalence rates differed, with the classification using multiplication by two being approximately six percentage points lower compared to the current guideline (IPAQ, 2005). These differences remained when observing the prevalence rates separately for men and women. Thus, when considering time scores weighted by intensity, prevalence rates may be underestimated, potentially limiting policy initiatives aimed at maintaining physical activity levels (Ács et al., 2020; Lee et al., 2011).

In this study, the prevalence of low physical activity levels, as classified by current IPAQ guidelines, was 36.7% among all university students, with significantly higher proportions observed in women (40.9%). Prevalence of low physical activity levels among university students, based on instrument guidelines, ranged from 8.1% (Murphy et al., 2018) to 15.31% (Pituk & Cagas, 2019) and 31.2% (Fontes & Vianna, 2009).

In research involving university students, there is limited use of this classification system to identify students at risk due to insufficient physical activity levels (Sousa, 2011; Kljajević et al., 2021; Silva et al., 2021). Thus, comparisons at a global level are limited. Physical activity is a crucial behavior across all age groups, and during university years, estimating and classifying at-risk groups becomes essential for better health promotion planning, although activity patterns may vary according to cultural aspects and educational systems (Kljajević et al., 2021).

This study has several limitations that warrant consideration. The use of questionnaires, which are prone to response bias, represents an initial study limitation. However, this instrument has been previously validated in different populations, including Brazilian samples, and demonstrates adequate psychometric properties for epidemiological research (Matsudo et al., 2001). On the other hand, this study's notable strengths enhance its credibility, including its sample size and sampling procedure encompassing university students from various academic programs, which contributes to greater generalizability of the findings.

Conclusion

The findings indicate substantial agreement between classifications with and without doubling vigorous-intensity physical activity time, particularly among women. However, the application of this weighting method resulted in considerably lower prevalence rates of physical activity compared to current IPAQ guidelines. The findings of this study provide valuable insights, underscoring the public health significance of this issue. The observed differences in prevalence rates and classification discrepancies highlight the need to reassess physical activity risk group identification procedures to inform evidence-based health promotion policies.

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